

Complexes of Antimony Trichloride with Organic Sulphides.

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In course of the present investigation, several compounds of antimony trichloride with some of the alkyl sulphides have been prepared and their behaviour studied in detail. These include:—

Antimony trichloride at ordinary temperatures dissolves in the liquid sulphides without any apparent reaction but reacts visibly at elevated temperatures (120° — 190°) in sealed tubes. The purification and crystallisation of these compounds require care, as they are sensitive to moisture.

The above compounds fall into two groups: I to IV and V and VI. Compounds (I-IV) are white crystalline substances, soluble freely only in acetone and insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform and many other non-hydroxylic solvents. The methyl sulphide compound is somewhat exceptional and turns orange-red, when treated with acetone. They are all decomposed by water or alcohols and first turn yellow gradually deepening to orange-red, as the decomposition proceeds. The ultimate product is antimony trisulphide. The yellow or orange-yellow intermediate compounds contain variable percentage of carbon and chlorine, which gradually decreases, as the treatment with water or alcohol is prolonged. The reaction has been studied in detail in the case of the ethyl and butyl sulphide compounds. With warm alcohol, other decomposition products, besides antimony sulphide, are formed and the following have been obtained:—

With water, these compounds could not be obtained but antimony oxychloride was detected, besides antimony sulphide. Treatment with boiling alcohol also causes similar decomposition.

An attempt was made to replace SbCl_3 by some other metallic chloride. An acetone solution of mercuric chloride, added to the compound, $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ in acetone, throws down at once a white precipitate, having the composition, $\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$. The other compounds react similarly. When treated with thiocarbamide in acetone, a yellow compound slowly crystallised. It was found to be $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$ (Vanino and Mussnug, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 21).

An acetone solution of silver nitrate with a solution of the same solvent gives a reddish-brown precipitate, consisting of antimony sulphide and silver chloride. The precipitation of the sulphide occurs only after the complete removal of chlorine as silver chloride. It is probable that at first a reaction in the sense of the equation, $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} + 3\text{AgNO}_3 = \text{Sb}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S} + 3\text{AgCl}$ takes place but the nitrate of antimony, being very unstable, is at once decomposed by ethyl sulphide to antimony sulphide.

When dry ammonia is passed into acetone solutions of these compounds, they decompose. Curiously enough, antimony sulphide was again the principal product of the decomposition. With caustic alkali, all the compounds decompose with the liberation of the respective sulphides.

Constitutional Formula.—From the mode of decomposition with water or alcohol, it seems probable that they are not mere addition compounds. On the addition of water, very little oxychloride is precipitated, the bulk of the compound being decomposed to antimony sulphide. This, as well as the reaction with ammonia, shows that an intimate union exists between the antimony atom and the alkyl sulphide group. It may be mentioned that no antimony sulphide is produced, if SbCl_3 and Et_2S are heated together with water. The simplest method of formulation, which suggests itself is $\text{Cl}_3 = \text{Sb} \dots \text{SEt}_2$. The conductivities are, surprisingly enough, greater than those of antimony trichloride at corresponding dilutions. The fact that all the chlorine is precipitated by silver nitrate in the cold seems to point to the possibility that all the chlorine atoms are ionisable.

The conductivity data in acetone solution, however, indicate that in acetone the compound is ionised into two ions and the molecular weight (184) as determined by the boiling point

method also supports this view. So that in acetone solution, the compound possibly behaves as

It is also possible that the antimony atom co-ordinates one or more acetone molecules, so that the usual co-ordination number 4 or 6 is satisfied. The conductivity values are shown in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Conductivity of SbCl₃ in acetone at 25°.

Data obtained by Kahlenberg and Lincoln (<i>J. Phys. Chem.</i> , 1899, 3, 12).		Data obtained by the author.	
Dilution.	Mol. conductivity.	Dilution.	Mol. conductivity.
7.07 litres	1.23 r. o.	55.20 litres	2.07 r. o.
14.14	1.55	110.40	3.30
28.27	1.83	220.80	3.81
56.56	2.13		
113.10	3.34		

TABLE II.

Conductivity of SbCl₃·Et₂S in acetone at 25°.

Dilution.	Mol. Conductivity in freshly prepared solution.	Dilution.	Mol. conductivity after 24 hrs.
308 litres	72.77 r. o.	236 litres	74.20 r. o.
616	81.56	472	80.79
1232	86.81	944	86.56
2464	92.30		
4928	94.62		

But a more plausible supposition is that the compounds have a constitution such as

of the sulphonium type. Such a constitution readily explains the conductivity as well as the close relationship between the sulphur and the antimony atoms. However, further investigation is desirable.

The reduction of mercuric chloride to the mercurous stage remains to be considered. This may be due to the tendency of $[\text{Sb...SEt}_2]\text{Cl}_3$ to pass into $[\text{Sb. SEt}_2]\text{Cl}_5$ just as K_2PtCl_4 is readily oxidised to K_2PtCl_6 .

Compounds (V) and (VI).—These are white crystalline substances with sharp melting points and freely soluble in alcohol but moderately so in acetone. With water the solutions decompose and antimony oxychloride is formed. These are additive compounds. Silver nitrate precipitates only silver chloride and hydrogen sulphide precipitates antimony sulphide from solutions of these compounds.

Compounds such as $2\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{HCl}$, $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $2\text{BiCl}_3 \cdot \text{HCl}$, $3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ resembling these compounds to some extent are quite well known.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$.—Antimony trichloride and ethyl sulphide were mixed together in molecular proportions. The trichloride dissolved in the sulphide with evolution of heat. The mixture was then heated in a sealed tube at $140\text{--}50^\circ$ for about six hours. The reaction product, a foul smelling black viscous mass, is insoluble in ether. Consequently the unchanged reactants which were soluble were removed by shaking several times with ether. The residue was dissolved in acetone, reprecipitated by ether and the process repeated till it was free from antimony trichloride and ethyl sulphide. It was redissolved in acetone and further purified by refluxing with animal charcoal. On evaporation, a light coloured viscous mass remained behind. In order to obtain it in a crystalline form, the compound was dissolved in a little acetone in a conical flask and ether was added, until a part of the substance was thrown down. The mouth of the flask was then loosely corked up and the vessel left for several days. A mass of tiny white crystals appeared, m. p. 143° .

The reagents and solvents should be free from moisture. With either of the reactants in excess, the same compound was obtained. (Found: C, 14.98; H, 3.31; Sb, 38.35; Cl, 33.51. $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 15.07; H, 3.14; Sb, 38.25; Cl, 33.44 per cent.).

Sulphur is found to be present. The presence of diethyl sulphide is indicated by its smell on warming with caustic alkali.

Preparation of $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{S}$.—The reactants were heated at $120\text{--}30^\circ$ as above. The dark viscous product was at first treated several times with ether. On addition of acetone, the compound gradually decomposed turning orange-yellow. The mass after treatment with ether was left in a vacuum desiccator for several hours, when white crystals gradually separated; these were washed several times with ether. (Found: C, 8.12; Cl, 37.05; Sb, 42.42. $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 8.29; Cl, 36.81; Sb, 42.10; per cent.). It was insoluble in the solvent.

Preparation of $4 \text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{-n-Bu}_2\text{S}$.—The reactants in the proportion of 2:1 were heated at $170\text{--}90^\circ$ as above. The resulting dirty syrupy mass was washed with ether as usual, dissolved in acetone, refluxed with animal charcoal. On evaporation of the acetone, a white granular mass, contaminated with a dirty substance, was obtained. The latter could not be eliminated by repeating the process. On adding a little alcohol in the cold (ice), the dirty oily substance passed into solution leaving behind a perfectly white granular mass. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator and crystallised from acetone.

TABLE I.

	Found.			Calc. for	Calc. for
	I.	II.	III.	$2\text{Sb}_2\text{Cl}_5(\text{OH}) \cdot 3\text{Bu}_2\text{S}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	$2\text{Sb}_2\text{Cl}_5(\text{OH}) \cdot 3\text{Bu}_2\text{S}$.
Sb,	36.65 } 36.06 }	36.95 } 36.47 }	36.50	36.09	37.07
Cl,	25.84 } 25.98 }	25.98	26.14	26.29	27.02
C,	21.13	—	20.97	21.33	21.92
H,	—	—	4.48	4.44	4.27
S,	—	—	6.54	7.11	7.31

The deficiency of chlorine, as well as the slightly variable percentage of antimony, indicate that the increased hydrolysis beyond the state $\text{Sb}_2\text{Cl}_5(\text{OH})$ takes place.

It is a white crystalline compound, m.p. 105° . It turns red at the melting temperature. The compound was next prepared in such a way that the presence of water was carefully excluded.

TABLE II.

Found			Calc. for	Calc. for
I.	II.	III.	$2\text{Sb}_2\text{Cl}_5(\text{OH})\cdot 2\text{Bu}_2\text{S}$.	$4\text{SbCl}_3\cdot 3\text{Bu}_2\text{S}$.
Sb, 37.55	36.69	36.54	37.07	36.06
Cl, 27.68	28.54	28.87	27.02	31.44
C, 22.34	—	—	21.92	21.30

This compound does not turn red at the melting point. The best results indicate that it is very difficult to avoid hydrolysis by moist air even when dry reagents are used.

$\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{Pr}_2\text{S}$ is a white crystalline compound, m.p., 124° . (Found: Sb, 34.91; Cl, 31.02. $\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{Pr}_2\text{S}$ requires Sb, 35.14; Cl, 30.75 per cent.).

Preparation of $2\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{HCl}\cdot 3\text{Bu}_2\text{S}$.—The compound $4\text{SbCl}_3\cdot 3\text{Bu}_2\text{S}$ was added to alcohol and gently warmed for about 2 hours. The orange-red antimony sulphide was removed by filtration and the filtrate left for two or three days, when white crystals were formed. (Found: C, 32.03; S, 9.78; Sb, 26.43; Cl, 27.12. $2\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{HCl}\cdot 3\text{Bu}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 30.94; S, 10.32; Sb, 26.16; Cl, 26.96 per cent.). It is a white crystalline compound with a sharp melting point at 125° .

Preparation of $2\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{HCl}\cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.—It was prepared exactly as above. It is a white crystalline compound, melts at 75° without apparent decomposition. (Found: C, 18.30; Sb, 31.90; Cl, 32.65. $2\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{HCl}\cdot 3\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 18.87; Sb, 31.93; Cl, 32.57 per cent.).

Preparation of $\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}$.—An acetone solution of mercuric chloride was added drop by drop to $\text{SbCl}_3\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ in acetone, until no further white precipitate was formed. The precipitate was filtered and washed several times with acetone.

It is a white amorphous voluminous mass when first prepared, gradually shrinking and hardening with drying; it darkens gradually and turns black after a few days. It is insoluble in the usual solvents but is dissolved by aqua regia, with precipitation of sulphur.

That mercurous mercury is present is shown by treating it with ammonia or caustic alkali, when it turns black. (Found: C, 8.08; Cl, 12.51; Hg, 70.50. $\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2\cdot\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 8.53; Hg, 71.30; Cl, 12.65 per cent.).